

Accessibility evaluation report

General objective: Conduct an initial accessibility review of the access to and data analysis of LSST Data Preview 1 (DP1) through the Rubin Science Platform (RSP), to identify barriers faced by Blind and Low Vision (BLV) users and provide preliminary recommendations for improvements.

Objective of this partial report: Review of DP1 and RSP interfaces; testing with screen readers on different platforms (reading, navigability, semantics, among others).

Resume

This accessibility review successfully achieved its objective of assessing access to and data analysis of LSST Data Preview 1 (DP1) through the Rubin Science Platform (RSP) to identify barriers for Blind and Low Vision (BLV) users. This assessment is intended as the first step in an iterative approach toward full inclusivity.

The evaluation confirms that the RSP provides a strong, accessible foundation in its core services. The account creation and login process is largely accessible, utilizing widely adopted authentication methods (like Google, ORCID, Microsoft, or GitHub) and clear, step-by-step guidance, which simplifies the process for users.

Of the three data access methods, the Notebooks aspect and the PyVO connection are highlighted as the most accessible. Notebooks' aspect offers better navigability and robust tutorial content, with the beneficial feature of multilingual support, specifically Spanish, in its introductory sections. While the general documentation is well-structured and navigable by screen readers, a specific improvement needed for the Notebooks aspect is ensuring screen readers detect the "Small" and "Large" server options as clickable buttons.

For the case of the PyVO API, there are difficulties in obtaining the token and the initial connection; however, after these steps are achieved, it can be used without issues from the command line.

Critical barrier:

1. **Language:** most information is presented in English, making it inaccessible for people that doesn't speak this language.

Moderate barrier:

1. **Usability Disruption in Firefly documentation:** A major usability issue found in the general documentation is the loss of the user's reading context upon returning from a link. Users are often forced to restart at the top of the page or manually search for their prior position, which significantly disrupts focus and workflow.
2. **API Challenges:** The API aspect presents the most significant barriers. Critical text is omitted by the NVDA screen reader on Windows during the challenging token generation process (*This is only a moderate barrier because the missing information is not critical to understand the tutorial*).

Low barrier:

1. **Contrast and Broken Links:** Minor issues include a low contrast ratio (5.25:1) in the video tutorial's red-on-black text, which falls below WCAG Level AAA standards, and the presence of broken links within the documentation (e.g., the IRSA Workspace webpage and the 'Roman documentation' link).
2. **Cognitive Load:** The Portal aspect is less accessible compared to the others due to the high cognitive load imposed on BLV users by the sheer quantity of fields and queries displayed (*This is considered a low barrier because there are two other ways to access the information, and these are more accessible*).
3. **TOPCAT problem with screen readers:** This API doesn't allow the use of screen readers inside it (*This is considered a low barrier because the PyVO option is available and more accessible*).

In conclusion, the identified issues—specifically the API authentication problems, the loss of reading context in the documentation, and the video contrast—represent key barriers that must be prioritized for remediation. These points could be addressed in the short or medium term.

For a more comprehensive and immediately useful experience for BLV users, two key recommendations are proposed. First, leveraging the existing **multilingual capability** observed in the Notebooks aspect—where the introductory sections feature an option to display content in Spanish—should be expanded across the entire platform's user-facing documentation and interfaces, enhancing accessibility for non-English speakers. Second, while users can currently employ browser zoom, the platform needs a **built-in feature to increase the default font size** without requiring a simple zoom function. This is necessary because current zooming does not re-adjust all on-screen elements to fit the viewable area, resulting in excessive horizontal scrolling and a diminished user experience, which is a significant barrier for users with low vision. Addressing these points would provide an enhanced and more flexible user experience for the target community.

Methodology

Tools used

During the accessibility analysis, various tools were utilized. Initially, automated accessibility evaluators were employed, specifically selecting Lighthouse (<https://chromewebstore.google.com/detail/lighthouse/blipmdconlkpinefehnmjammfijmpbjk?hl=es&pli=1>) and WAVE (Web Accessibility Evaluation Tool - <https://wave.webaim.org/>). Lighthouse is an open-source tool integrated with the Google Chrome browser. WAVE is a tool available via its website, which is more focused on accessibility analysis and WCAG guidelines, maintaining a user-centric philosophy.

Subsequently, for manual testing, screen readers integrated with the respective operating systems were used: VoiceOver for macOS, and Orca for Linux. For Windows, NVDA (NonVisual Desktop Access), an open-source screen reader for that platform, was used. The methodology involved navigating the different sections of the website using the screen reader's description and the keyboard, and documenting every problem encountered during navigation.

Focus Group testing

The user-based analysis was conducted in two stages. First, an analysis was carried out with the Bioengineering Institute's working group, which included two professionals with experience in accessibility analysis and the English language. In this stage, the general deployment of the main websites was reviewed, along with two tutorials from the Portal section and two tutorials from the Notebooks section by each evaluator.

Subsequently, a guided walkthrough was conducted through the main site and the Notebooks section with visually impaired individuals. Recruitment was carried out by telephone with people living in Mendoza, Argentina, as an in-person evaluation was planned. Two visually impaired individuals participated, both of whom had experience in using technology but not in data analysis or Astronomy. The focus group experience was carried out using a series of instructions that required the participants to navigate the sites autonomously to complete the tasks. The overall results presented in this report are derived from both experiences.

Detailed analysis

Link to the platform(1): <https://data.lsst.cloud/>

Documentation of Data Preview 1 (DP1) (2): <https://dp1.lsst.io/>

Tutorials of DP1 (3): <https://dp1.lsst.io/tutorials/index.html>

Generation of a new account on the platform

The next tutorial was followed: <https://rsp.lsst.io/guides/getting-started/get-an-account.html>

The tutorial's step-by-step description is detailed and precise. It is considered sufficient; no problems or setbacks were encountered during the login process. The use of widely known platforms like Google, ORCID, Microsoft, or GitHub simplifies the process for users.

The account creation process was completed using a screen reader, which reproduced all the steps without issues. Although the Guide links to external sites, the inclusion of clear navigation buttons at the end of each section ensures a smooth user experience.

A point to mention is the need for email verification. This step can complicate navigation for visually impaired users, as they must: find their email application, wait for the message, and refresh the screen until it appears before they can continue. It is understood that this is a necessary security measure, and it is only required for the first login. A positive point is that this step maintains consistency with the requirements of widely used websites.

Regarding the video available in the login tutorial, the information is considered adequate. A point for improvement is the use of red text on a black background, which has a contrast ratio of "5.25:1." The WCAG Level AAA requires a contrast ratio of at least 7:1 for normal text. Take into consideration that the use of red text on a black background can cause significant eye strain and make reading difficult, especially for people with visual impairments or color blindness. The suggestion is adding a text box with a white background for messages when the website is in dark mode, if the same text color is to be maintained throughout the video (since it is also used on a light background, where it is appropriate).

It is concluded that the login process is both accessible and consistent with how other platforms handle sign-in. It uses authentication methods that are conventional in scientific fields like astronomy and astrophysics. The only aspect noted for improvement is a contrast detail with some of the written messages in the video tutorial (red-on-black contrast).

Automatic evaluation

The testing tools used were Lighthouse and WAVE (Web Accessibility Evaluation Tool), specifically for the three web pages at the beginning. The automatic evaluation couldn't be done with the webpage that requires a login.

In summary, the automatic evaluation carries good results, the errors arise missing alternative text in three icons (Fig. 1), but is considered not necessary because the icons represent the previous title (these are located in the main page <https://data.lsst.cloud>).

Fig. 1 - Icons without Alt-Text.

The other accessibility problem was the contrast in the day color mode of the tutorials. This problem was only found with the links, where the color mode was the only way to identify them, and didn't present a good contrast ratio. This problem doesn't appear in the night color mode.

General Documentation

The general documentation webpage describes all expected topics and has a simple layout, which allows for good navigation with screen readers. It provides links to navigate between different sections, with each topic having its own page, resulting in coherent content. It is noteworthy that it includes navigation elements at the end of each page, a top menu, and a menu to the right of the main section, all of which do not interrupt navigation with the screen reader.

A great feature is that the interface of the different documentation pages is consistent, with element groups remaining in the same place. A navigation panel on the left is only added for the user guide and overview sections.

A crucial point is the ability to return to the user's previous location on the page after clicking a link and then navigating back. Currently, when a user follows a link and then returns, they are often forced to restart at the top of the webpage or manually search for their prior reading position. This loss of context significantly disrupts the user's focus and workflow.

The IRSA Workspace webpage (Fig. 2) is returning a 404 error (<https://data.lsst.cloud/docs/workspace>).

Fig. 2 - Firefly documentation, section Loading Images.

From the Firefly documentation, Visualization tools tab, the 'Roman documentation' link (Fig. 3) is also broken.

Fig. 3 - Firefly documentation, Visualization tools, end of the page.

In general, the other parts of the documentation are good; they are well understood and are consistent with what they intend to explain.

Platform sections

The project offers three data access methods from the start: a portal, notebooks, and an API. The portal format displays data using multiple fields, a common approach in most astronomical databases. While this format has accessibility challenges, maintaining consistency with existing systems is an acceptable practice to ensure the majority of users can access the data. On the other hand, the notebook format is increasingly used within data analysis communities, as it allows for real-time work with libraries and visualization of graphs. This format offers significant improvements in accessibility and navigation for screen reader users. Finally, the API format provides an option to use applications, such as the

command line, to access the data. This adds versatility and allows researchers to use the application that best suits their needs. Each format has its own documentation.

Portal

The portal tool is considered less accessible due to the quantity of notebooks and queries. It is noteworthy that it can be navigated with screen readers; the limitation stems from the high cognitive load required for a person with a visual disability to recall the large number of elements available on the screen.

Regarding the tutorials and the navigation of the portal section, they are considered adequate. The tutorials are detailed and allow for recognition tasks to become familiar with the location of elements in the interface. If possible, I would add access to the documentation from within the portal section.

Notebooks

In this case, the navigability is better. In the first screen with the server option, the NVDA screen reader doesn't detect that Small and Large are clickable buttons. If it is possible, I suggest changing it to checkboxes.

Server Options

Image	Options
<p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Recommended (Release r29.2.0, RSP Build 2244)</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Release r29.2.1 (RSP Build 2332)</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Weekly 2025_43</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Weekly 2025_42</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Daily 2025_10_26</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Daily 2025_10_25</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Daily 2025_10_24</p> <p><input type="radio"/> Select uncached image (slower start):</p> <p>Recommended (Release r29.2.0, RSP Build 2244) ▾</p>	<p><input type="radio"/> Small (1.0 CPU, 4Gi RAM)</p> <p><input checked="" type="radio"/> Large (4.0 CPU, 16Gi RAM)</p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Enable debug logs</p> <p><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Reset user environment: relocate .cache, .conda, .config, .eups, jupyter, .local, and .user_setups</p>

[Start](#)

Fig. 4 - Server option for the Notebook aspect.

The initial setup and server access process were highly efficient and quickly completed using the recommended settings.

The onboarding process, however, presents some minor inconsistencies. The introductory welcome page provides a general overview, but its explanation regarding the tutorials is slightly confusing. Specifically, the initial difficulty lay in determining whether the user should

start a new notebook or execute the tutorial steps within the provided example notebooks (e.g., DP0.2).

Once past the initial confusion, the tutorial content itself is strong. Key accessibility and usability highlights include:

- **Multilingual Support:** The introductory sections of the tutorials feature an option to display content in Spanish, which enhances accessibility for non-English speakers.
- **Clarity and Detail:** The initial steps are well-explained and provide essential context for the actions being performed, including basic commands for server connection, image visualization, data table truncation, and database filtering.
- **Resource Availability:** The system effectively integrates the documentation for the utilized libraries, which is a valuable resource for users needing immediate reference or clarification.
- **Performance and Robustness:** The provided code executed rapidly and consistently across environments, successfully running both within the designated tutorial notebook and when manually transferred to a newly created notebook. The support for exporting data to Pandas further enhances usability.

After that, we proceeded to execute advanced tutorials, specifically the "Galaxy Cluster Weak Gravitational Lensing Analysis" and the "Milky Way Dust Extinction Correction" notebooks. The structure of these advanced tutorials proved highly effective, as each began with a comprehensive introduction outlining the concepts and the prerequisite libraries needed for execution. The content was easily followed and executed without issue. Notably, the code performed robustly, yielding identical data and images whether executed directly within the provided tutorial notebook or replicated in a new, independent notebook. Furthermore, the execution time for these more complex analyses was consistently fast, indicating efficient performance across the platform.

APIs

Following the documentation to generate the Token (<https://rsp.lsst.io/guides/auth/creating-user-tokens.html>), we found that point 5, using Screen Reader (NVDA on Windows), omits the text between "Create" and "somewhere secure on your local system." (Fig. 2). In contrast, on Ubuntu with Orca Screen Reader, the complete sentence could be read.

Fig. 2 - Missing text using Screen Reader

The token generation process is challenging; it requires copying the key text from a pop-up window, saving it in a safe place, and accessing it again to be used from a third-party app. At this point a button to copy the token would be a very useful tool. In addition, when I try to create the user token without entering a name (the window shown in Fig. 3), no error is displayed. The system stays on the same window, does nothing, and gives the impression that it's frozen/not functioning.

Fig. 3 - Token generation window

Once the token is generated, two options are described in the documentation. First, the TOPCAT program uses several pop-up windows where the person has to access and login with the generated key to be able to access the data sets. Second, the PyVO package, related to the astropy package. This package is intuitive and could be used from the command line. In both cases, I found a problem with the authentication using the token generated. In addition, I couldn't find a specific tutorial about the use of pyvo.

TOPCAT

As mentioned, TOPCAT uses several pop-up windows. Furthermore, the program, which is coded in Java, does not allow its components to be read by screen readers such as Orca. It is considered a difficult tool for visually impaired people to use.

PyVO

In the case of PyVO, a tutorial for establishing the connection was not found; instead, it redirects to the PyVO website. The problem was encountered when trying to log in, given that the main PyVO documentation does not have a clear example for using a Token.

After several attempts, I contacted Andrés Plazas Malagón, who gave me the code to establish the connection with the Token. I was able to connect successfully and test one of the Jupyter Notebook tutorials

(https://jcasado.nb.data.lsst.cloud/nb/user/jcasado/lab/tree/notebooks/tutorials/DP1/300_Science_Demos/303_Galaxies/303_1_Galaxy_photometry.ipynb) from the command line using Python and PyVO. As can be seen in Fig. 4, the connection and the database query were performed without any problems.

Fig. 4 - Image plotted with matplotlib following the tutorial from the link mentioned in the text.

Link error:

During the searching tutorial to connect the APIs, I visited the next webpage <https://rsp.lsst.io/guides/api/>. At the end, in the Additional Resources section, the link under the word 'tutorials' was broken; it said 'WebPage not found' in Spanish (the specific broken link is <https://rubinobservatory.org/es/for-scientists/resources/tutorials>).

NOTE: All the findings and detailed descriptions in this analysis, as well as the preliminary recommendations for improvement, are directly derived from the initial independent accessibility assessment of the interfaces and the essential user testing sessions. This methodology ensures that the identified barriers accurately reflect the real-world challenges encountered by the target community when interacting with the Rubin Science Platform (RSP) and DP1 data.

Recommendation about sonification

Background

Sonification is an evolving field dedicated to the use of non-speech audio to represent information and data. It is formally defined as "the transformation of data relations into perceived relations in an acoustic signal for use as an alternative sense to study the data set". This technique integrates a wide variety of professional fields and leverages the highly developed human sense of hearing as a complementary tool to traditional data visualization (Diaz-Merced et.al., 2011). Sonification can be considered a specific type of sound design, where the resulting sounds are explicitly linked to the underlying data (Zanella et.al., 2022).

The utility of sonification in scientific data analysis stems from the inherent advantages of the human auditory system (Fovino et.al., 2024). Sound is fundamentally multi-dimensional, characterized by parameters such as pitch, volume (loudness), tempo, location in a stereo field, and timbre. The human ear excels at processing multiple audio streams simultaneously, a feature related to the "cocktail party effect", which enables the listener to detect weak information amidst background noise (Cooke et.al., 2017). Furthermore, the auditory system is significantly more sensitive to sudden temporal variations compared to its visual counterpart.

Benefits and Application in Data Analysis

Sonification provides numerous benefits for researchers, including the ability to: analyze complex or rapidly changing data, explore large or multi-dimensional datasets, examine data in frequency dimensions rather than spatial ones, and identify new patterns or phenomena that current display techniques might miss or mask (Tucker Brown et.al., 2022; Diaz-Merced et.al., 2011). This technique is also valuable for monitoring data in the background while performing other tasks.

A crucial motivation for the development of sonification tools is accessibility, particularly for individuals who are blind or vision impaired (BVI). Traditional reliance on visualization creates a significant barrier for BVI individuals seeking careers in astronomy (Zanella et.al., 2022). Sonification offers an alternative display modality to ensure the accessibility of astronomy from schools through to the academic environment.

Sonification Techniques and Tools

One of the most common sonification approaches is parameter mapping. This method ties sound characteristics—such as pitch, volume, or timbre—directly to data parameters. Pitch is frequently the most utilized auditory dimension in astronomy applications, often associated with the dependent variable, such as brightness. Other parameter mapping studies have investigated the use of duration.

In the field of astronomy and space science, sonification has a documented history dating back to 1962, when Donald Gurnett began using sound to analyze and convey information from space missions like Cassini and Voyager (Zanella et.al., 2022). Notable historical examples of the utility of sonification include identifying frequencies in Chandra X-Ray observations of the cataclysmic variable EX Hya and detecting the characteristic "machine gun" sound caused by micrometeoroids that signaled a problem with the Voyager 2 space mission (Diaz-Merced et.al., 2011).

The number of sonification projects in astronomy has grown rapidly, particularly since 1996, with nearly 80% of known projects developed between 2011 and 2021 (Angelidakis et.al., 2024). Several modern sonification tools have been developed to address the complexities of astronomical data:

- xSonify: A Java-based prototype designed to analyze two-dimensional data, such as time-series, which has been used for space physics and X-ray astronomy data.
- ASTRONIFY: An open-source Python package intended for sonifying one-dimensional data like light curves and spectra, with plans to incorporate the functionality into the Barbara A. Mikulski Archive for Space Telescopes (MAST) (Tucker Brown et.al., 2022).
- StarSound: A standalone software designed for the sonification of multi-dimensional datasets, offering accessibility features through a user interface or a text-based configuration file (Foran et.al., 2022).
- sonoUno: An open-source platform developed with a user-centered design approach, providing multimodal (visual and auditory) deployment of 1D astronomical data like light curves and spectra, enabling scientific analysis and catering to users with and without disabilities (Casado and García, 2024).
- STRAUSS: This is a Python-based, open-source sonification package available on GitHub. It was designed for scientific analysis, but also for scientists to create sonification for public outreach. STRAUSS aims to improve the current visual display of data and enhance accessibility (Trayford and Harrison, 2023).

Current Status and Challenges

Despite the growing number of projects and documented successes, sonification is not yet integrated into mainstream research tools and remains a niche approach. One major barrier is the lack of standardized approaches for representing data through sound. Furthermore, there is a recognized lack of systematic published evaluation concerning the effectiveness and usability of sonification methods, particularly for research purposes.

Efficacy testing, such as studies investigating parameter mapping for time-series data, suggests that while sonification can enable the detection of high Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) signals, performance for medium and low SNR data is significantly lower compared to visual plots for experienced astronomers. This disparity suggests that effectiveness is hindered by a lack of training and familiarity in interpreting sonified data (or "reduced listening") within the scientific community, emphasizing that training is crucial for realizing the potential of sonification in professional astronomy.

Conclusion

This accessibility review successfully achieved its general objective: to conduct an initial accessibility review of the access to and data analysis of LSST Data Preview 1 (DP1) through the Rubin Science Platform (RSP) to identify barriers for Blind and Low Vision (BLV) users and provide preliminary recommendations for improvements. The evaluation confirmed that the RSP establishes a strong, accessible foundation in its core services. Specifically, the account creation and login process is largely accessible, utilizing widely

adopted authentication methods (such as Google or ORCID) and clear, step-by-step guidance. Of the three data access methods, the Notebooks aspect and the PyVO connection are highlighted as the most accessible.

Despite this foundation, the assessment identified several key barriers that must be addressed to achieve full inclusivity:

- 1. Critical Language Barrier:** The most critical barrier is that the majority of information is presented in English, rendering it inaccessible for non-English speakers.
- 2. Documentation Usability:** A major usability issue exists in the general documentation: the loss of the user's reading context upon returning from a link. Users are often forced to restart at the top of the page or manually search for their prior position, which significantly disrupts focus and workflow.
- 3. API and Authentication Challenges:** The token generation process is challenging. During this process, the NVDA screen reader on Windows omits critical text. Furthermore, the TOPCAT program, coded in Java, does not allow its components to be read by screen readers such as Orca, making it difficult for visually impaired people to use. The Portal aspect is also considered less accessible due to the high cognitive load imposed by the sheer quantity of fields and queries displayed.
- 4. Low Contrast and Broken Links:** Minor issues include a low contrast ratio (5.25:1) in the video tutorial's red-on-black text, which falls below the WCAG Level AAA standard of 7:1. Additionally, broken links were found in the documentation (e.g., the IRSA Workspace webpage and the 'Roman documentation' link).

The identified issues—specifically the API authentication problems, the loss of reading context in the documentation, and the video contrast—represent key barriers that should be prioritized for remediation in the short or medium term.

Two key recommendations are proposed for a more comprehensive and immediately useful experience for BLV users:

- 1. Expand Multilingual Support:** The existing multilingual capability, observed in the introductory sections of the Notebooks aspect (where content is offered in Spanish), should be expanded across the entire platform's user-facing documentation and interfaces.
- 2. Implement Font Sizing Feature:** It is necessary to provide a built-in feature to increase the default font size without requiring simple browser zoom, which currently causes excessive horizontal scrolling and a diminished user experience for users with low vision.
- 3. Place a button to copy Token:** It is useful to place a button that allows the user to copy the text on the token window, it is more accessible to BLV users.

In the broader context of enhancing accessibility, sonification is an evolving field that offers a crucial alternative modality. Sonification, defined as the transformation of data relations into an acoustic signal for interpretation, leverages the inherent advantages of the human auditory system, which is multi-dimensional and excels at processing simultaneous audio

streams. Reliance on traditional visualization creates a significant barrier for BVI individuals seeking careers in astronomy; therefore, sonification offers an alternative display modality. Modern tools like STRAUSS and sonoUno aim to improve current visual display of data and enhance accessibility, specifically within the astronomical domain.

However, sonification remains a niche approach due to a lack of standardized methods and a recognized lack of systematic published evaluation concerning its effectiveness for research purposes. Efficacy testing suggests that while sonification is effective for high Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) signals, performance drops for medium and low SNR data compared to visual plots for experienced astronomers. This highlights that training and familiarity in interpreting sonified data are crucial for realizing its potential in professional astronomy. Integrating robust sonification tools and training alongside the necessary interface accessibility improvements (language, font, token process) would provide a comprehensive, versatile, and inclusive user experience for the astronomical community.

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